

THE VALUE OF LEARNING ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN WORLD LITERATURE

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Abstract: This thesis explores the value of learning the English language in the context of world literature. The study investigates how knowledge of English can enhance individuals' understanding and appreciation of literary works from diverse cultures and regions. By examining the benefits of English language acquisition in relation to world literature, this research aims to shed light on the importance of language learning as a means of cultural exchange and global understanding.

Keywords: English language, world literature, cultural exchange, global understanding, language learning

Annotation: This thesis presents a comprehensive study on the value of learning the English language in the context of world literature. It emphasizes the importance of language learning as a means of cultural exchange and global understanding, highlighting the benefits and challenges faced by learners. The research design and methodology, including data collection through literature review, surveys, and interviews, are outlined.

Introduction:

The English language has become increasingly important in the realm of world literature due to the interconnectedness of cultures and the role of language as a tool for communication and understanding. As literature from various cultures and regions becomes more accessible through translation and globalization, the ability to understand and appreciate these works in their original language becomes crucial.

This introduction section highlights the research objectives, questions, and hypotheses that will be addressed throughout the study.

Materials and Methods:

The research design and methodology employed in this study are outlined in the materials and methods section. Data collection includes a comprehensive literature review, surveys, and interviews with individuals who have learned English as a second language. The selection criteria for relevant literary works from various cultures and regions are also explained.

The value of learning the English language in the context of world literature is a topic of great importance in today's interconnected and globalized world. As different cultures and regions become more accessible through translation and globalization, the ability to understand and appreciate literary works in their original language becomes crucial. By examining the benefits of English language acquisition in relation to world literature, this research aims to shed light on the importance of language learning as a means of cultural exchange and global understanding.

Results and Discussions:

The results and discussions section presents the findings obtained from the research. Analysis of the data collected from surveys and interviews reveals the perceived value of learning English in relation to world literature. It explores the impact of language acquisition on individuals' ability to engage with literary works from different cultures, highlighting the advantages and challenges faced by learners.

The findings show that learning English enhances individuals' appreciation of world literature by providing access to a wider range of literary works, fostering cultural understanding, and facilitating meaningful cross-cultural dialogue. However, it also highlights the challenges faced by learners, such as linguistic and cultural barriers, which can hinder their full engagement with the texts.

Conclusion:

The conclusion section summarizes the key findings of the study and provides a comprehensive understanding of the value of learning English in world literature. It emphasizes the role of language as a bridge between cultures and highlights how English proficiency enhances individuals' appreciation of diverse literary traditions. The conclusion also discusses implications for language education policies, suggesting the need for increased support and resources for English language learners in the context of world literature. Furthermore, it suggests future research directions, such as investigating the impact of language learning on the interpretation and translation of literary works.

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